

Recommended citation: Strozzi, F., Noè, C., Colicchia, C., & Creazza, A. (2017). Teaching Sustainability to Engineers: A Systematic Literature Review. In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 87-94). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14697999.

Teaching sustainability to engineers: a systematic literature review

F.Strozzi⁽¹⁾

Associate Professor
Carlo Cattaneo University-LIUC
Castellanza (VA), IT
E-mail: fstrozzi@liuc.it

C.Noè

Full Professor
Carlo Cattaneo University-LIUC
Castellanza (VA), IT
E-mail: c.noe@liuc.it

C.Colicchia

Senior Lecturer
Business School, Hull University
Hull (UK)
E-mail: C.Colicchia@hull.ac.uk

A.Creazza

Senior Lecturer
Business School, Hull University
Hull (UK)
E-mail: A.Creazza@hull.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Since the publication of the UN-sponsored World Commission on Environment and Development report [1] in 1987, thousands of initiatives have been undertaken to address the different aspects of environmental challenges [2]. Among these initiatives, in 2002 the UN General Assembly proclaimed the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development, 2005-2014, 'emphasising that education is an indispensable element for achieving sustainable development'.

Sustainability has been on the agenda of many engineering faculties since the late 1990s [3]. It has become clear that "a new kind of engineer is needed, an engineer who is fully aware of what is going on in society and who has the skills to deal with societal aspects of technologies" [4]. Literature covering this topic is abundant. The discussion on how sustainability can be successfully integrated into engineering programmes is still receiving attention.

This paper aims to present a literature review focused on sustainability in engineering education. The review is based on the Systematic Literature Network Analysis (SLNA), a methodology including a collection of computer-based tools that analyses bibliographic data, and that have been applied to the continuous improvement of Higher Education [5]. The SLNA is adopted in this work in order to unfold the dynamics of sustainability in engineering education and identify the directions in which engineering faculties are moving.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education; Curriculum Development; Engineering Education Research.

Keywords: Sustainability development, education, curriculum development, Systematic Literature Network Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The first definition of sustainability development was given by World Commission on Environment and Development (Brundtland Commission) in 1987 and states that sustainability development is the "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". To pursue this policy, Education on Sustainable Development (ESD) was recognised by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) to play a major role in this process. ESD is a main activity of UNECE, which, together with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), implemented a road map for ESD in 2005. The road map consisted of three steps: Phase I (2005-2007), i.e. Stocktaking, where the Member States had to identify existing initiatives; Phase II (2008-2010), i.e. Integration, where the Member States had to begin the integration of SD in the curricula; Phase III (2011-2015), i.e. Implementation, where the Member States had to ensure the introduction of ESD in every school and promoting teachers' education.

The final comment in the report published after the end of Phase III (May 2016, [6]) was that "significant advancements have been made on four of the seven Strategy issue areas: *policy integration, curricula, tools and resources, and cooperation and networking*" but "more systematic attention should be given to progress on non-formal and informal learning, and special consideration given to advancing ESD research, monitoring and evaluation as essential inputs to strengthening ESD".

Hence, in order to contribute to advancing ESD the goal of this paper is to depict a landscape of the scientific literature on SD in the curricula of engineers through the adoption of the dynamic literature review method called "Systematic Literature Network Analysis (SLNA)". This method was introduced by [7] and combines the systematic literature review approach with bibliographic network analyses. The successful adoption of such an approach to other contexts, e.g. [8], [9], [10], proves its potential value in the identification of research trends and evolutionary trajectories.

2. Material and methods

SLNA starts with the application of a systematic procedure (Systematic Literature Review, SLR) to identify and select relevant papers. Then, the selected papers are analysed using bibliometric tools, such as the Citation Network Analysis (CNA) that provides information on the evolution of the more active research areas; the citation is assumed to represent the influence of the cited work on an author's new work [11].

The first phase, i.e. SLR, includes the following steps: *scope of the analysis*, to define the boundaries of the study; *locating studies* to retrieve papers from databases through keywords, search strings and other criteria (e.g. type of document, time window); *study selection and evaluation*, to isolate the most relevant papers.

The second phase of SLNA takes into account the papers selected in the first phase and applies bibliographic network analyses and network visualisation tools.

Nevertheless, delineating and representing a research field only by means of papers linked by citations may lead to biased results since some important contributions, even if their content is relevant, may be not yet cited due to various causes. For this reason, the results of citation network analysis is combined with those provided by other bibliometric tools.

Papers were collected from the Scopus database, which is, together with Web of Science (WoS), the most commonly used scholar citation database. Scopus is very

similar to the WoS database but Scopus has a wider coverage [11]. To build the citation network VoS Viewer (<http://www.vosviewer.com/>, [31]), a software package able to analyse bibliometric networks, was adopted. The citation network was then studied using Pajek [13] which is a software package for Social Network Analysis.

3. First phase of SLNA methodology: SLR

3.1. Scope of the analysis

As mentioned in the introduction, many efforts have been made by international organisations to introduce SD concept into the educational curricula. The scope of the analysis of this paper is to find research directions in the field of engineering education on SD and to understand if the interest of international organisations was reflected in the content of the papers analysed.

3.2. Locating study

For locating the study it is necessary to define some keywords. The keywords were discussed with a panel of experts composed of mechanical and environmental engineers. It is important to underline that this step of the analysis is very critical to reduce the individuals' bias. The final search string used in Scopus is as follows: 'curricul*' AND 'development' AND 'sustainability'. This was searched in the field "keywords", which includes author keywords and keywords assigned by Scopus and the Engineering area was selected.

3.3. Study selection and evaluation

The search was performed on April 2017, without any restriction on document type (conference paper, article, review, article in press, letter) and on time window (the first document dates to 1990): 267 documents were retrieved.

4. Second phase of SLNA methodology: bibliographic network analyses

The works identified in the first phase were used as input for the second phase of SLNA. A local analysis using citation network was performed to detect the evolution of the main concepts. Some of the 267 papers may be not included in the citation network but cited many times in Scopus and then a complementary analysis of the most cited papers in 2016 in Scopus was performed.

4.1. Citation Network Analysis (CNA)

To perform CNA it is firstly necessary to exclude the isolated nodes that are papers nor cited neither citing others in the network. This is the case of 188 documents. The remaining 79 documents form connected components. In details, 68 documents form a big connected component and the remaining papers are connected in other four small components. The amount of information that can be extracted from the biggest component is more structured than the one emerging from small components with only a very limited number of connected nodes [10]. Based on this consideration, only the connected component with 68 documents will be analysed.

4.1.1. The analysis of the Biggest Connected Component

Figure 1 depicts the biggest connected component. To analyse this component the Main Path (MP) algorithm [12] was used. MP extracts main trends in the evolution of paper contents identifying papers that constitute part of the backbone of the research

tradition. This backbone is composed of papers lying on the shortest paths between source and sink nodes. A source is a paper cited by but not citing other papers of the network while a sink is a paper citing but not cited by other papers of the network.

Figure 1. The biggest connected component of the citation network.

In [14] it has been observed that the MP obtained in this way provides the most significant path. Nevertheless, if a discipline has many sub-areas, this is not enough to uncover all the milestones of the research tradition. [14] propose to relax some constraints of the process to build the MP to generate the so-called *key-route*. In Figure 2 the *key-route* of the biggest connected component is presented. The papers range from 2009 to 2017 and the flow of knowledge shows a change in the research interests in engineering education on SD, starting from the need to present a systemic and holistic vision of SD passing through the development of instruments helping to develop a curriculum to arrive, recently, to the development of measures to quantify the SD content of curricula or to quantify learning outcomes related to SD.

- *The need for a systemic vision of sustainability development.*
[15] suggested to involve external stakeholder in the curriculum development; [16] observed that SD in engineers' curricula helps students to think using system theory perspective including social, environmental, economic and technical aspects. [17] stated that the competencies on sustainability, provided by many courses, are fragmented and this calls for adjusting programmes of study to embrace a system thinking approach. A holistic approach is highlighted by [18] too, which suggested introducing geography in the SD curriculum due to its strong tradition within the human-environment theme.
- *Instruments helping the integration of sustainability development in the curriculum.*
[19] proposed a very accessible teacher's manual for SD integration. [20] presented a process for developing a curriculum in Engineering for SD. They succeed to represent and integrate different courses using Concept Maps and 'Sustainability Tool for Assessing Universities' Curricula Holistically" (STAUNCH). [21] proposed a web-based sustainability portal to support curriculum renewal based on a sequence of workshops and meetings that help teachers to meet the needs of students.

Figure 2. The *key-route* of the biggest connected component.

- *Necessity to quantify the learning outcomes and the content of curricula* . The importance of quantifying learning outcomes was underlined by [22]. [23] proposed an index (Relevant Ratio) to measure the amount of content on SD of curricula. This ratio indicates the weight of sustainability topics in a programme.

Moreover, the necessity to organise the works on the curricula on SD is shown by [24] where 33 papers on curriculum development in higher education institutions are commented; [25] demonstrated that an approach to engineering education strongly based on problem-solving is an obstacle for a complete understanding of SD; [26] analysed 25 top master programmes worldwide for urban development; [27] proposed a mixed approach based on qualitative (thematic groups) and quantitative (survey pre and post assessment) techniques in a multidisciplinary class of students. The methodology was tested and the advantages and disadvantages presented.

The research directions identified in the *key-route* works have been then compared with the aim of the UNECE initiative, to understand their degree of alignment even if none of the papers was funded by this framework. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between the UNECE initiative and the research directions identified in the *key-route*.

Time window	UNECE Phases	<i>key-route</i> Papers
2005-2007	Phase I. <i>Stocktaking</i> : the Member States had to identify existing initiatives;	
2008-2010	Phase II. <i>Integration</i> : the Member States had to begin the integration of SD in the curricula;	The necessity of a systemic vision and the stakeholders' involvement [15]. Development of instruments for the integration of SD: a teacher's manual [19] . A method for developing a curriculum in SD engineering [20].
2011-2015	Phase III. <i>Implementation</i> : the Member States had to ensure the introduction of ESD in every school and to promote teachers' education and measuring the outcomes.	Necessity to quantify the learning outcomes and the curricula contents ([22], [23]). Obstacles to the implementation of the ESD [25] .

In particular, it is interesting to observe that during Phase II (i.e. Integration), some papers were published on practical tools for the integration of SD into curricula, while

during Phase III (i.e. Implementation) papers related to quantifying learning outcomes, content and implementation obstacles appear ([22], [23] and [25]). It is possible to conclude that the UNECE initiative, reflected in many national initiatives, influenced research directions in the engineers' curriculum development on SD.

4.2. Global Analysis

As mentioned, it is necessary to cross the information provided by citation network with a global analysis. The first step consists in analysing all the papers from the point of view of distribution over time, authors and journals. In Figure 3 the 267 papers by year of publication are represented. A fast increase starts after 2007 and this is interesting in the light of the efforts of the international organisations after 2005. The number of works seems to reach a plateau around 2014 (data on 2017 is partial). Most of the works are conference papers or articles. The most productive authors are Lozano R. and Ceulemans K. who authored/co-authored many papers of the *key-route* too. Another author appearing in the *key-route* is Ferrer-Balas D. who wrote the oldest paper of 2009, which seems a milestone of the research tradition. The journal more often publishing papers on this subject is *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Also all papers on the *key-route* are published in this Journal.

Figure 3. Number of works published over time.

Another shortcoming of the citation network and of the *key-route* is their inability to isolate papers gaining attention recently, since they did not have time to be cited or because they are cited by papers not included in the connected component. In Table 2 the ranking of the most cited papers in 2016 is provided together with the evolution of the number of citations they received in Scopus over time.

Table 2 - Ranking of the top cited papers in 2016.

Rank	Publication year	Reference	Part of the connected component (CC) and Key-Route (KR)	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
1	2011	[28]	CC	0	2	5	13	6	11	12	0
2	2013	[29]	isolated node	0	0	0	1	6	0	10	2
3	2010	[30]	CC	1	2	3	21	7	17	8	2
4	2014	[22]	CC and KR	0	0	0	0	0	7	8	5
5	2015	[24]	CC and KR	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	4
6	2010	[19]	CC and KR	0	2	1	10	7	17	7	2

Among the top six papers, three belong to the connected component and to the *key-route*. The first three works ([28], [29], [30]), although not very recent, seem to have recently acquired interest and this deserves special attention. [28] studied, using a survey, the introduction of Building Information Modeling and sustainability in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) curricula. The importance of

education on SD for civil engineering it is not a new theme but it is recently gaining more importance due to the fast development of new materials and technologies and the related employment opportunities. [29] proposed a new methodology for the introduction of SD in the curricula of the energy engineers using multimedia internet-based technology. [30] is a review of the papers presented at the 5th Environmental Management for Sustainable Universities, an international conference held in 2008 in Barcelona (Spain). Some of the top ranked papers are literature reviews (traditionally receiving many citations) but the presence of [28] and [29] showed the higher level of importance of SD for AEC and Energy engineering than for other areas.

5. SUMMARY

In this paper we have applied SLNA to perform a literature review of the research on the introduction of SD in engineers' curricula. The necessity to perform research and develop tools to this end is recognised and fostered by UNECE. The analysis using citation network highlights an alignment between research directions and the UNECE initiative, i.e. the implementation of tools to help teachers to introduce SD in the curricula and the development of new measures to quantify the SD content of curricula or to measure the learning outcome. The ranking of the most cited papers in 2016 pointed out two additional papers not included in the *key-route*, which show a great interest in the introduction of SD especially in curricula of energy engineers and AEC. This can be due to the fast development of new material and technologies and the employment opportunities in these areas. Hence the importance to pay attention to SD becomes even more important. Nevertheless, even if this analysis shows the general importance to introduce SD in the engineers' curricula, it seems that efforts have concentrated mostly on some specific areas (AEC and energy) while other areas seem overlooked (e.g. industrial ([32],[33]) or electronic engineering). As [25] point out, "a deeper change in the engineers' vision is necessary to change their mode of engagement with the world and their ability to tackle root causes of social and environmental issues in technologically advanced society".

REFERENCES

- [1] WCDE, World Commission on Environment and Development (1987), *Our Common Future*, Oxford University Press, p. 27. ISBN 019282080X.
- [2] Mebratu, D. (1998). Sustainability and sustainable development: historical and conceptual review. *Environmental impact assessment review*, 18(6), pp. 493-520.
- [3] Segalas, J., Ferrer-Balas, D. and Mulder, K.F. (2010), What do engineering students learn in sustainability courses? The effect of the pedagogical approach, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 18(3), pp. 275-284.
- [4] De Graaff, E. and Ravesteijn, W. (2001), Training complete engineers: global enterprise and engineering education, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 26(4), pp. 419-427.
- [5] Colicchia, C., Creazza, A. and Strozzi, F., 2017. Citation network analysis for supporting continuous improvement in Higher Education. *Studies in Higher Education*, pp.1-17.
- [6] UNECE, 10 years of UNECE Strategy for Education for Sustainable Development (May 2016), Available on <http://www.unece.org/index.php?id=45227>.
- [7] Colicchia, C. and F. Strozzi. 2012. "Supply chain risk management: a new methodology for a systematic literature review." *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 17(4): 403-418.
- [8] Kajikawa, Y., Ohno, J., Takeda, Y., Matsushima, K. and Komiyama, H. (2007), Creating an academic landscape of sustainability science: an analysis of the citation network. *Sustainability Science*, 2(2), pp.221-231.
- [9] Kim, S., Colicchia, C. and D. Menachof, D. (2016), Ethical Sourcing: An Analysis of the Literature and Implications for Future Research." *Journal of Business Ethics*, doi:10.1007/s10551-016-3266-8.
- [10] Strozzi, F., Colicchia, C., Creazza, A., Noè, C., (2017). Literature review on the "Smart Factory" concept using bibliometric tools, Accepted in *International Journal of Production Research*.

- [11] Zhao, D. and Strotmann, A. (2015), Analysis and visualization of citation networks, *Synthesis Lectures on Information Concepts, Retrieval, and Services*, 7(1), pp. 1-207.
- [12] Lucio-Arias, D., and Leydesdorff, L. (2008), Main-path analysis and path-dependent transitions in HistCite™-based historiograms, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59(12), pp. 1948-1962.
- [13] De Nooy, W., A. Mrvar and Batagelj, V. (2011), *Exploratory social network analysis with Pajek*, (Vol. 27), Cambridge University Press.
- [14] Liu, J. S., and Lu, L. Y. (2012). An integrated approach for main path analysis: Development of the Hirsch index as an example. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(3), pp. 528-542.
- [15] Ferrer-Balas, D., Buckland, H., and de Mingo, M. (2009), Explorations on the University's role in society for sustainable development through a systems transition approach. Case-study of the Technical University of Catalonia (UPC), *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 17(12), pp. 1075-1085.
- [16] Pappas, E., Pierrakos, O., and Nagel, R. (2013), Using Bloom's Taxonomy to teach sustainability in multiple contexts. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 48, pp. 54-64.
- [17] Lambrechts, W., Mulà, I., Ceulemans, K., Molderez, I., and Gaeremynck, V. (2013), The integration of competences for sustainable development in higher education: an analysis of bachelor programs in management, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 48, pp. 65-73
- [18] Grindsted, T. S. (2015), Educating geographers in an era of the anthropocene: paradoxical natures—paradoxical cultures, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, pp. 320-329.
- [19] Ceulemans, K. and De Prins, M. (2010), Teacher's manual and method for SD integration in curricula. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 18(7), pp. 645-651.
- [20] Lozano, F. J., and Lozano, R. (2014), Developing the curriculum for a new Bachelor's degree in Engineering for Sustainable Development, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 64, pp. 136-146.
- [21] Rose, G., Ryan, K. and Desha, C. (2015), Implementing a holistic process for embedding sustainability: a case study in first year engineering, Monash University, Australia, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, pp. 229-238.
- [22] Adomssent, M., Fischer, D., Godemann, J., Herzig, C., Otte, I., Rieckmann, M. and Timm, J. (2014), Emerging areas in research on higher education for sustainable development—management education, sustainable consumption and perspectives from Central and Eastern Europe, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 62, pp. 1-7.
- [23] Mälkki, H., Alanne, K. and Hirsto, L. (2015), A method to quantify the integration of renewable energy and sustainability in energy degree programmes: a Finnish case study, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, pp. 239-246.
- [24] Ramos, T. B., Caeiro, S., van Hoof, B., Lozano, R., Huisingsh, D. and Ceulemans, K. (2015), Experiences from the implementation of sustainable development in higher education institutions: Environmental management for sustainable universities, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, pp. 3-10.
- [25] El-Zein, A. H. and Hedemann, C. (2016), Beyond problem solving: Engineering and the public good in the 21st century, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, pp. 692-700.
- [26] Bina, O., Balula, L., Varanda, M. and Fokdal, J. (2016), Urban studies and the challenge of embedding sustainability: A review of international master programmes, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, pp. 330-346.
- [27] Sharma, B., Steward, B., Ong, S. K. and Miguez, F. E. (2017), Evaluation of teaching approach and student learning in a multidisciplinary sustainable engineering course, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, pp. 4032-4040.
- [28] Becerik-Gerber, B., Gerber, D. J. and Ku, K. (2011), The pace of technological innovation in architecture, engineering, and construction education: integrating recent trends into the curricula, *Journal of Information Technology in Construction (ITcon)*, 16(24), pp. 411-432.
- [29] Klemeš, J. J., Kravanja, Z., Varbanov, P. S. and Lam, H. L. (2013), Advanced multimedia engineering education in energy, process integration and optimisation, *Applied energy*, 101, pp. 33-40.
- [30] Ferrer-Balas, D., Lozano, R., Huisingsh, D., Buckland, H., Ysern, P. and Zilahy, G. (2010), Going beyond the rhetoric: system-wide changes in universities for sustainable societies, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 18(7), pp. 607-610.
- [31] Van Eck, N. J. and Waltman, L. (2010), Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping, *Scientometrics*, 84(2), p. 523-538.
- [32] Pozzi, R., Noè, C. and Rossi, T., 2015. Experimenting 'learn by doing' and 'learn by failing'. *European journal of engineering education*, 40(1), pp.68-80.
- [33] Noè, C., Pozzi, R. and Magni, A., 2015. Teaching sustainability to industrial engineering students. In *Proceedings of the 43rd SEFI annual conference 2015-diversity in engineering education: an opportunity to face the new trends of engineering*, SEFI 2015. European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI).